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Periodontal Regeneration in Mandibular Intrabony defects using DFDBA with chorion membrane vrs DFDBA with collagen membrane and I-PRF augmentation in mandibular supra-bony defects: A Split Mouth Case Report

Divjot Kaur Narula¹
 Pooja Palwankar²
 Kanishk Gupta³
 Kriti Aggarwal⁴
 Priyadarshini⁵

PG Student¹
 Department of Periodontics and Oral Implantology
 Santosh Dental College and Hospital
 Ghaziabad

Professor²
 Department of Periodontics and Oral Implantology
 Santosh Dental College and Hospital
 Ghaziabad

Head³
 Department of Periodontics and Oral Implantology
 Santosh Dental College and Hospital
 Ghaziabad

Reader⁴
 Department of Periodontics and Oral Implantology
 Santosh Dental College and Hospital
 Ghaziabad

Senior Lecturer⁵
 Department of Periodontics and Oral Implantology
 Santosh Dental College and Hospital
 Ghaziabad

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Abstract

This split mouth case study evaluates the regeneration effectiveness of injectable platelet rich fibrin (I-PRF) augmentation for related suprabony lesions and demineralized freeze dried bone allograft (DFDBA) in conjunction with either chorion or collagen membranes in mandibular intrabony defects. Clinical and radiological characteristics were assessed at baseline and six months after regenerative treatment for a systemically healthy patient with bilateral periodontal abnormalities. The DFDBA chorion membrane site showed marginally better tissue integration and radiographic bone regeneration, although both membrane assisted DFDBA techniques produced significant decreases in probing depth, increases in clinical attachment, and considerable defect fill. In suprabony deformities, concurrent use of I-PRF improved early soft-tissue healing and supported overall surgical results. This paper emphasizes the combined effects of membrane selection and biologic augmentation in promoting periodontal regeneration.

Introduction

The American Academy of Periodontology (AAP) has defined regeneration as the reproduction or reconstitution of a lost or injured part to restore the architecture and function of the lost or injured tissues.¹

Intrabony defects, one of the many signs of periodontitis, are a limited vertical loss of bone next to teeth that can be very difficult to treat clinically. If treatment is not received, these defects which are categorized according to the number of residual bone walls (one, two, or three wall defects) are linked to an increased risk of tooth loss and disease development. For such osseous defects, a variety of therapy options have been investigated, most likely including autogenous grafting or bone substitutes such xenografts, allografts, and alloplasts. Guided tissue regeneration (GTR) for selective cell development, stimulation of cells with various growth factors, hormones, or extracellular matrix proteins, and modification of the tooth root surface using various materials are other methods that have been studied.²

GTR involves covering the region surrounding the injured tooth root surface with a barrier membrane, which may be resorbable or nonresorbable. This will enable the periodontal wound's progenitor cells to repopulate in a targeted manner.³

Despite the serious drawbacks of non resorbable membranes, type I collagen based membranes are the most widely employed

of the several biodegradable natural and synthetic membranes now on the market.⁴ The minimal immunological response, capacity to promote cellular development and attachment, homeostasis, and the ability of collagen solutions to reconstitute into the microfibrillar structure found in natural tissues are all specific benefits of resorbable collagen membrane.⁵

Derived from the fetal membrane, chorion membranes provide a wealth of growth hormones and extracellular matrix components that promote angiogenesis, differentiation, and cell proliferation, all of which aid in periodontal regeneration. Growth factors such as Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) and Platelet Derived Growth Factor AA (PDGF-AA), together with chemokines and anti-inflammatory cytokines, are released by the chorion membrane.⁶ CM has angiogenic, anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties.⁷

Demineralized Freeze Dried Bone Allograft (DFDBA), which has been used extensively as a bone graft material in conjunction with these membranes, offers osteoconductive scaffolding and osteoinductive potential through bone morphogenetic proteins to speed up the creation of new bone. It is made by

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xtracting cortical sections of bovine bone in 100% ethanol and ethyl ether for one hour. After that, it is ground up in a liquid nitrogen mill, demineralized for three hours in 0.5 N HCl, and cleaned with water, anhydrous ether, and absolute ethanol until the pH is neutral.⁸

Clinical studies have demonstrated that the combination of collagen or chorion membranes with DFDBA leads to superior regenerative outcomes compared to either approach alone. Parameters such as probing pocket depth reduction, clinical attachment level gain, and radiographic bone fill have consistently shown improvement, particularly in well contained two and three wall intrabony defects. The synergistic effect of the membrane as a barrier and the graft as a scaffold creates an environment conducive to periodontal regeneration, minimizing postoperative complications and enhancing the predictability of the treatment. Thus, the management of periodontal intrabony defects using collagen membranes, chorion membranes, and DFDBA represents a cornerstone in regenerative periodontics, combining biological principles with clinical efficacy to restore form and function to the periodontium.

Case Presentation

A 35 year old male patient came to the OPD of periodontics and oral implantology, Santosh Dental College, Ghaziabad with the chief complain of food lodgement in lower right and left posterior region of the jaw in the last 3 months. After clinical examination a pocket of 5 and 7 mm was found in lower left (figure 1) and right (figure 2) first and second molars respectively. A Cone Beam Computed Tomography was planned and intrabony defects was found in lower left (figure 3) and right (figure 4) first and second molars and suprabony defect was found in the lower anterior region. To rule out systemic problems and find out if the patient has been taking medication for a long time, a comprehensive medical history was taken, a thorough hematological examination was carried out. Patient was advised regenerative mucoperiosteal flap surgery.

Surgical Intervention

After obtaining informed consent from the patient, local anesthesia, Xicaine 2% with adrenaline (one in 80,000) was administered, and a sulcular incision was given extending from 35 to 37 region. After reflection of full thickness flap, thorough root debridement with area specific Gracey curettes was done, the defect was visualized. (figure 5a and b) Demineralized Freeze Dried Bone Allografts (Tata Memorial Tissue Bank, Mumbai) was mixed with saline and was condensed inside the defect (figure 6 a and b). Collagen membrane (Collaguide) was used to cover the graft as a barrier membrane (figure 7). The same was followed for 45 to 47 region and Chorion membrane (Tata Memorial Tissue Bank, Mumbai) was used to cover the graft as a barrier membrane (figure 8). 3-0 silk (Lotus) sutures were used. (figure 9a and b)

Figure 1: probing pocket depth with 36 and 37 is 5 mm.

Figure 2: Pre-operative probing depth with 46 and 47 is 7mm

Figure 3: Pre-operative CBCT measurements with 36

Figure 4: Pre-operative CBCT measurements with 46

Figure 5: exposing the defect with 36,46

Figure 6 a: Before graft condensation with 36

Figure 6 b: Before graft condensation with 46

Figure 7: Collagen membrane placement with 36

Figure 12: 9 months Post-operative probing pocket depth measurement = 3 mm

Figure 8: Chorion membrane placement with 46

Figure 13: 9 months Post-operative CBCT measurement with 36

Figure 9 : Post-operative suture with 36

Figure 14: 9 months Post-operative CBCT measurement with 46

Figure 10: Post-operative suture with 46

The Lower anterior region had a probing pocket depth of 5mm (figure 15). This anterior suprabony/horizontal defect was treated by giving sulcular incision from 13-23 and full thickness flap was reflected. Thorough root planning and root debridement was done with area specific gracy curettes (figure 16). Under aseptic conditions 10ml of venous blood was withdrawn from the cubital fossa and was transferred into plastic EDTA tubes with a counterweight of betadine. Choukran's method was used to make I-PRF that is 700rm for 3 minutes with the help of centrifuge machine (Remi) (figure 17). This I-PRF was injected onto the supra-bony defect in the lower anteriors (figure 18). 3-0 silk sutures were used to close the flap (figure 19).

Figure 11: 9 months Post-operative probing pocket depth measurement = 4 mm

Figure 15: Probing Pocket Depth of 5mm

Figure 16: Reflection and debridement

Figure 17: Centrifuge machine with plastic EDTA tubes

Figure 18: Injecting I-PRF after Open Flap Debridement (OFD)

Figure 19: Post-operative sutures

Post-operative Care

The appropriate antibiotics and analgesics (amoxicillin 500 mg three times a day and piroxicam twice a day for five days), respectively were recommended, along with 0.2% chlorhexidine mouthwash twice daily for two weeks. Sutures were removed one week postoperatively. Patients were instructed on oral hygiene

maintenance and recalled on a weekly basis for the first month, followed by six and nine month recall protocol.

Discussion

Both treatment modalities DFDBA with collagen membrane and DFDBA with chorion membrane produced clinically and radiographically substantial improvements in the management of mandibular intra-bony abnormalities, as the current split-mouth case report showed. On the other hand, locations treated with the chorion membrane showed better increases in clinical attachment level and somewhat larger decreases in probing pocket depth. These results are consistent with the physiologic benefits of placental derived membranes, which are rich in extracellular matrix proteins, growth factors, and intrinsic anti-inflammatory qualities. Chorion membranes are superior to traditional collagen barriers because of their high tensile strength, delayed resorption, and favorable matrix that promotes periodontal ligament and bone cell growth (Aziz et al., 2016)⁹ Gurinsky (2009)¹⁰ reported enhanced regenerative potential with amniotic/chorionic tissues due to their intrinsic bioactive components that support wound healing and reduce postoperative inflammation.

Collagen membranes, on the other hand, lack the biological stimulatory qualities of chorion tissues and serve mainly as passive barriers that maintain space, despite being widely employed and well documented. Collagen membranes are biocompatible and useful in directed tissue regeneration, according to studies by Mellonig (1992)¹¹ and Murphy et al.¹² (1995) However, their quick rate of resorption may restrict long-term space maintenance in specific defect shapes. Therefore, the structural constraints and absence of intrinsic bioactive chemicals in collagen membranes may be the reason for the very small gains seen in this work.

All treated sites showed significant radiographic decreases in defect breadth and depth together with an increase in defect angle, indicating good bone fill and defect resolution. This is in line with research by Lekovic et al. (1998)¹³ who showed that intra-bony defect architecture, including width and angle, directly affects regeneration results, with smaller and more acute flaws generally providing greater spatial stability for clot and graft development.

Over the course of the nine months, the graft matured and the osteoconductive environment improved, as seen by the significant rise in defect angle in this instance.

Soft-tissue healing was also enhanced by the supplemental use of injectable platelet rich fibrin (i-PRF) for supra-bony lesions. i-PRF stimulates angiogenesis and fibroblast proliferation by continuously releasing growth factors like PDGF, TGF- β , and VEGF. According to Miron et al. (2017),¹⁴ i-PRF's liquid fibrin network speeds up maturation and improves soft-tissue healing when compared to conventional PRF formulations. Therefore, the clinical benefits shown in this case's supra-bony regions are consistent with previous research showing that i-PRF can enhance both soft-tissue stability and early wound healing.

Overall, the chorion membrane's physiologically active matrix, which promotes periodontal regeneration beyond mere barrier function, may be responsible for the better results observed with it. This is consistent with the general agreement that membranes with structural integrity and natural growth factors might enhance regeneration predictability. Although this case report's sample size restricts its generalizability, the findings support the body of research that suggests placental derived membranes and biologic adjuncts are potential agents for periodontal regeneration.

Conclusion

The combination of DFDBA and barrier membranes produced clinically and radiographically significant periodontal regeneration in mandibular intra-bony defects, within the constraints of this split mouth case study. Although both collagen and chorion membranes supported positive results, the chorion membrane showed relatively better improvements in defect morphology, clinical attachment gain, and probing depth reduction. This is probably because of its inherent bioactive qualities and increased capacity for wound healing. Effective bone fill and maturation over the assessment period were further validated by radiographic decreases in defect breadth and depth as well as an increase in defect angle. Additionally, early stabilization and better soft-tissue healing were facilitated by the supplementary use of i-PRF in supra-bony defects.

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